

CONTINUOUS FIBERS TAILORED LONG FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY

This work focuses on processing and performance evaluation in terms of static and dynamic properties of LFTs co-molded with pre-consolidated CFRTs, referred to as Endless Long Fiber thermoplastic (E-LFT). The E-LFT approach is an alternative to rib / grid stiffened composites. The effect of CFRT's thickness and fiber type on mechanical properties of E-LFTs is evaluated. The static and dynamic results are then compared to LFT samples (with and without ribs). Design applications featuring LFTs and E-LFTs are also discussed

Keywords: Long Fiber Thermoplastics, Continuous fiber thermoplastic (CFRTs), Dynamic Response

INTRODUCTION

Long Fiber Thermoplastics (LFT) are finding increased use in the automotive and transportation sector due to their superior specific strength and modulus resulting in substantial weight savings, combined with relative ease of fabrication and handling. LFT composites constitute a family of composites, wherein a thermoplastic matrix such as polypropylene, polyethylene, polyamide, poly phenylene sulfide or polyurethane is reinforced with discontinuous fibers. Some of the common applications for LFTs in the automotive industry include; dashboard carriers, front ends, seat shells, battery trays and spare wheel dwells. In several of these applications, increased stiffness, crashworthiness and enhanced damage tolerance is highly desirable. One way of incorporating damage tolerance in LFT thermoplastic composite parts is to use continuous fiber thermoplastics tapes that are co-molded with the LFT.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The LFT material used in this study was E-Glass / Polypropylene. 40% (w/w) fiber weight fraction, fiber pellets of 25 mm length was used. Samples with / without ribs and E-LFT were processed using the above LFT material. The three different types of pre-consolidated continuous fiber thermoplastics used are; E-Glass / Polypropylene, S2-Glass / Polypropylene both of fiber weight fraction of 70% (w/w) and Carbon / Polypropylene with a fiber weight fraction of 50% (w/w). All of the above materials were characterized for static three-point flexure and low velocity impact response, and the failure modes were analyzed post-failure using microscopy techniques.

KEY RESULTS

E-LFTs show increased properties compared to LFT irrespective of the fiber type used on the tapes. E-LFT specimens have enhanced flexural properties compared to LFTs

with and without ribs for equivalent flexural rigidity. The mode of failure in static loading is more ductile as opposed to a brittle failure that is exhibited in regular LFT specimens. E-LFT specimens show a second stage of increase in load after the initial failure (Figure 1). Both maximum flexural stress and displacement of E-LFT specimens are higher than all the LFT specimens. Under dynamic loading conditions the E-LFT specimen exhibit higher deflections, with increased load (normalized load) bearing capabilities leading to higher energy absorption. The studies on the mechanical properties provide a good indication of the possible use of these materials, especially where the design freedom by using LFT could be combined with the performance characteristics of the E-LFTs.

Figure 1. Comparison of E-LFT flexural results for varying fiber types on tape

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